

MERLIN: INCREASING THE QUALITY AND RATE OF MULTILAYER PACKAGING RECYCLING WASTE

Development of New Processes for the Sorting, Delamination and Recycling of Multilayer Plastic Packaging Waste

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INTRODUCTION

In this paper the technological areas related to packaging end of life involved in **MERLIN** are resumed: (1) development of technology based on packaging identification and characterization for the **sorting** of multilayer packaging, (2) separation and recovery of the constituent multilayer packaging by **delamination**, (3) recovery and reprocessing for **recycling** of the delaminated fractions, and (4) production and **validation** of upcycled packaging with the materials developed in the project.

1. GENERAL

In 2020, 29.5m tonnes of post-consumer plastic waste were collected in Europe. Only 34.6% of this plastic packaging was recycled, while 42% was incinerated and 23.4% was landfilled¹. This is still far from the target of recycling 55% of plastic by 2030, as set out in the European Plastics Strategy² and Directive (EU) 2018/852 on Packaging and Packaging Waste³. Currently, the market is demanding a large proportion of multilayer packaging, a kind of structure difficult to detect in sorting plants, as current technologies can only identify their surface layer. Once sorted, their recyclability depends on complex methods to separate their layers, as the different nature of the polymers makes them incompatible. In addition, the high-strength adhesive used to bond the layers together requires existing delamination processes to be improved and optimized. This result in multilayer packaging being landfilled or incinerated and requires improved sorting and recycling processes for this kind of plastic waste, which is currently not recovered from post-consumer sources.

MERLIN focuses on the identification of multilayer rigid, non-metalized flexible and metalized flexible packaging, and its recycling, developing a specific recovery process for each of them. The different fractions of plastics recovered present in the structures are separated and recycled and repolymerized fractions are used for the development and validation of packaging demonstrators, including recyclability and food contact evaluations.

Figure 1 Merlin project cycle diagram

2. THE MERLIN PROJECT

2.1.Sorting: Packaging identification

For the identification of mono-material packaging and monolayer films, the most widely used technology is NIR technology. However, the identification of multilayers with this technology is limited, due to the current commercially available technologies. These limitations increased in case of metalized polymeric multilayer films.

To overcome these technical limitations, MERLIN project is developing an innovative recognition system able to recognise not only different combinations of multilayer polymeric films but also metalized and polymeric multilayer packaging. This system will couple monitoring technologies supported with artificial intelligent algorithms in order to identify the presence of multilayer packaging residues and the composition of the different layers of the structure. The previous recognition system developed at MERLIN is coupled with an **artificial intelligence powered robot** and artificial intelligence machine vision detection techniques based on convolutional neural network to reduce operation times in the sorting plant, allowing efficient sorting of multilayer packaging in the waste stream, including rigid (trays) and flexible material (films).

2.2.Delamination: Separation & recovery

Delamination is the process used to separate the different layers, depending on the nature of the packaging, and within MERLIN, a set of separation processes, designed for each type and structure, is used:

Depolymerization is based on the chemical recycling of polyesters (PET) by catalysed solvolysis. This process allows the PET layer of rigid packaging structures to be recovered. PET solvolysis processes are based on the cleavage of the reduced chain into low molecular weight products, in the form of monomers and prepolymers.

For non-metalized films, **green solvent-based processes** have been developed. Hansen solubility parameters have been studied to reduce interlayer interaction and to achieve delamination by solvents under supercritical conditions (e.g., CO₂) in combination with green solvents. After both processes, the different PET and polyolefin (PO) fractions of the structures are separated and provisionally recovered.

The **solvent-based** solutions to be used for the metalized films exploit the dissolution properties of non-polar solvents like tertiary amines or other lipophilic biobased solvents. These solvents preserve the quality of the aluminium by preventing oxidation and recovery can be achieved traditionally or by changing the polarity of the solvent using CO₂ addition.

2.3.Recycling: Recovery & reprocessing of recovered material

The different fractions of PET and POs present in the structures are separated and recycled in MERLIN, depending on the delamination process used.

Repolymerizing the PET from the monomers and oligomers obtained, and reprocessing the recovered delaminated fractions with improved properties, in order to achieve the high requirement, form rigid and flexible packaging market.

2.4.Validation: Upcycled packaging development

The recycled and repolymerised fractions are used for the development and validation of packaging demonstrators, including recyclability and food contact evaluations.

The different **packaging prototypes** for rigid and flexible applications will be tested and their properties compared with similar virgin material solutions on the market. Finally, a **risk assessment in food contact** of the developed prototypes has also been carried out to study the possibility of their use in food contact applications.

REFERENCES

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